

THE TENSILE BEHAVIOR OF HYBRID FIBER REINFORCED
POLY (ETHERSULPHONE) COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The tensile mechanical properties of unidirectional hybrid composites fabricated from carbon / glass and carbon / Kevlar fiber in poly(ethersulphone) (PES) matrix have been evaluated over a variety of hybrid ratios and states of dispersion of two components.

The "Hybrid Effect" is also observed in the composites. The carbon / glass hybrid composites show the positive hybrid effect which increases with the decrease of relative content and with the more fine dispersion of carbon fiber. The tensile failure modes are governed by hybrid ratio and the degree of dispersion. In the case of low hybrid ratio, the carbon component shows multiple fracture, the length between two adjacent fracture points being 4.4 millimeters. The carbon / Kevlar hybrid composites show little positive or negative hybrid effect. The moduli of all the hybrid composites obey the simple mixture rule.

KEYWORDS: Tensile; Hybrid; Poly (ethersulphone) / PES; Fracture.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the past decades, great progress has been made in developing hybrid composites containing two or more types of fibers in a common matrix¹. It is most common that high

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cost, high modulus and low impact carbon fiber (CF) is hybridized with low cost, low modulus and high impact glass fiber (GF) or Kevlar fiber (KF) to balance rigidity, strength and toughness of composites and obtain a wide variety of structure and performance. Many investigators have made a number of studies on hybrid composites, especially, hybrid carbon / glass composites²⁻⁹, and found a phenomenon termed "Synergistic Strengthening"⁵ or "Hybrid Effect"⁶⁻⁹. The hybrid effect first credited to Hayashi¹⁰ is based on the essential observation in which the tensile failure strain, and hence the strength of low-elongation (LE) fiber is usually higher in a hybrid than in an all-LE fiber composite. Meanwhile, multiple fracture of LE component appears frequently in the hybrid structures.

In the former studies, the interests were mainly focused on the effects of types of component fiber, lay-up sequences and dispersion on the properties and hybrid effect, generally, in a thermosetting system, and attention was seldom paid to hybrid thermoplastic composites. It is clearly true that the toughness of matrix not only affects the range of hybrid effect, but also dominates the mode of failure. In the recent decade, the studies and applications of advanced thermoplastic composites with many advantages over conventional thermosetting system have been greatly developed¹¹⁻¹⁴.

It is undoubtedly important to study and evaluate hybrid thermoplastic composites.

In this paper, a primary study on hybrid fiber reinforced poly (ethersulphone) (PES), a typical thermoplastic matrix, has been made, and hybrid effect up to 42% and progressive multiple fracture have been observed.

2. EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Fiber and Resin Fibers used in the present work are T300 carbon fiber (6K, produced by Toraca Co. in the late 1970s), S-2 glass fiber (produced by Nanjing GF institute, in P. R. China) and Kevlar-49 aramid fiber (produced by Dupont Co.). PES with glass transformation temperature of 225°C is manufactured in our lab.

2.2 Prepregs Using a lab-size impregnating device, unidirectional prepregs of carbon, glass, Kevlar and intermingling fiber were manufactured. The fibers through a solution of PES were arranged on the heating drum and dried in-situ to form a tape with thickness of 0.125 to 0.13mm. The fibers were distinctly calibrated to avoid additional strain.

2.3 Fabrication Unidirectional hybrid laminates were fabricated in plate form by hot-press moulding technique. After the prepregs were cut into proper size and stacked carefully to lay-up configurations designed in a mould with the dimension of 230 × 140mm, the moulding was preformed on a hydraulic press for 20min at

320–335°C. The thickness of laminates with 16 plies of lamina and fiber volume fraction of 58–61% is 2.0mm. The fundamental properties of unidirectional carbon, glass and Kevlar fiber reinforced PES composites are given in table 1.

2.4 Lay-up Sequence In the present work, three types of laminate configurations were used: (a) interply or sandwich, (b) intraply and (c) interply / intraply. Table 2 shows the baseline parameters such as lay-up sequence, fiber fraction, symbol and so on.

2.5 Test Method Using Instron 1185 universal testing machine, tension test was performed in accordance with ASTM D3039–76 standard. The crosshead speed was 2mm/min for all the specimens. The strain before fracture were measured using a special Instron averaging extensometer which drove the chart recorder, and the whole fracture process was followed through a distance testing system attached to the instrument.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Tensile Modulus The stress-strain curves are virtually linear up to the first failure event. Figure 1 shows the relationship between initial moduli and hybrid ratios for two types of hybrid composites. The experimental data lie approximately on the line connecting the moduli of component materials, which confirm that the initial moduli of HF / PES composites obey the simple mixture rule as equation (1):

$$E_h = E_{LE}\chi_{LE} + E_{HE}\chi_{HE} \quad (\chi_{LE} + \chi_{HE} = 1) \quad (1)$$

Where E_h , E_{LE} and E_{HE} are initial moduli of hybrids, LE component and HE component, respectively; and χ_{LE} (regarded as hybrid ratio) and χ_{HE} are volume fraction of individual component.

3.2 Strength and First-failure Strain When the strain of a hybrid composite reaches that of LE component, theoretically, LE fiber will fracture and the first failure of the material will occur. The initial failure strength, σ_i , and inferior failure stress loaded by HE component σ_u , may be expressed as equation (2) and (3), respectively.

$$\sigma_i = E_h \varepsilon_{LE} \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_u = \sigma_{HE} \chi_{HE} \quad (3)$$

Experimental results given in table 3 show that the initial failure strength, hence initial failure strain of carbon / glass hybrids is much higher than those of theoretical values.

Hybrid effect (defined as $Re = [\varepsilon'_{LE} - \varepsilon_{LE}] / \varepsilon_{LE} \times 100\%$) is controlled by the degree of dispersion, and affected by the hybrid ratio as well. Figure 2 gives a more comprehen-

sive description. The hybrid effect increases with the decrease of relative content of carbon fiber and with the more fine dispersion of carbon fiber. CG-2, with the least hybrid ratio and the finest dispersion, showed the highest hybrid effect up to 42%. In contrast, CG-4, a sandwich construction with the out-layer of carbon, showed the smallest hybrid effect of 18.8%.

Carbon / Kevlar hybrids showed insignificantly positive or negative hybrid effect, which was primarily contributed to residual tension strain of carbon fiber in C / K hybrids and weak interface bonding between the two components.

3.3 Fracture Analyses The Fracture modes of hybrid composites are closely correlated with the hybrid ratio. There exists a critical hybrid ratio, χ_{cr} , on which the load to fracture of LE component is equal to what can be carried by the HE component and the ultimate strength is the lowest. χ_{cr} may be formulized as

$$\chi_{cr} = 1 - \left[1 + \frac{E_{HE}}{E_{LE}} \left(\frac{\epsilon_{HE}}{\epsilon_{LE}} - 1 \right) \right]^{-1} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{or } \chi_{cr} = 1 - \left(1 + \frac{\sigma_{HE}}{\sigma_{LE}} - \frac{E_{HE}}{E_{LE}} \right)^{-1} \quad (5)$$

Considering hybrid effect, it is necessary to replace the ϵ_{LE} or σ_{LE} with experimental values ϵ'_{LE} or σ'_{LE} in hybrids to analyse fracture modes exactly. The calculated values of χ_{cr} are listed in table 2. With $\chi_{LE} < \chi_{cr}$, HE component will be capable of carrying the extra load transferred to it resulting from the fracture of LE component until it fails.

As a result, the hybrid laminates may display two-step fracture mode, or several failures may occur in the LE component before finally the catastrophic failure of the HE component. In the case of $\chi_{LE} > \chi_{cr}$, extra load transfer from fracture of LE component can not be born by the HE component, so that one-step fracture mode will turn up.

Similar to those of GF / Ep composites, the failure of GF / PES and KF / PES laminates initiated by longitudinal splitting which progressed to total collapse of the specimen. CF / PES laminate failed by the rapid propagation of a transverse crack, with only limited longitudinal splitting. The stress-strain curves given in figure 3 show four kinds of fracture modes of C / G hybrid laminates. CG-3 and CG-7 show brittle fracture, which is attributed to high hybrid ratio and fine dispersion. In the case of CG-4 and CG-5, two sandwich constructions with hybrid ratio less than critical value, a typical two-step fracture was observed. Owing to low degree of dispersion, delamination in only interfaces of two components must be large enough to absorb the strain energy release from the fracture of carbon component and continues to progress with the extension of strain until glass component fails, which makes multiple fracture

impossible. As a result, the stiffness of the whole specimen after the first failure successively fell off, and the second failure stress (ultimate strength) was well in accordance with those of theoretical values and ultimate elongation was close to that of all-glass laminate.

The fracture modes of CG-1 and CG-8 with hybrid ratio slightly higher than their own critical value lay between one-step and two-step fracture. Due to high degree of dispersion, the stress penetration and strain energy release generated from fracture of carbon component were too great to be sustained by glass component, which led to the fracture of the neighbouring but non-total glass fiber, with serious longitudinal splitting and delamination. The rest of the glass component continued to carry relatively low load to final fracture of the specimen.

A progressive multiple fracture found out by many workers^{6,8,9} was also observed in HF / PES composites such as CG-2 and CG-9. Because of fine dispersion and low hybrid ratio, the strain energy release produced by the first fracture of carbon-ply was absorbed by the local delamination cracks, propagation of transverse cracks in carbon-ply was restrained and terminated by neighbouring glass-ply. Since there was finite length of delamination, the load could pass across the delamination interfaces and a region of stress transfer, and be diffused back into carbon-ply, with an extension of strain. Many transverse cracks scattering evenly on the whole gauge were observed, the length between two adjacent cracks being constantly 4.4 mm.

The fracture mode of CK-3, with obvious longitudinal splitting and pull-out of Kevlar fiber, is similar to that of CG-3. Two-step failure occurred in CK-1 and CK-2.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The hybrid thermoplastic composites described in this paper exhibit outstanding tension properties. The values of elastic moduli are well in agreement with those given by the mixture rule up to the first fracture event of carbon component. The C / G hybrid laminates all show positive hybrid effect of initial fracture strain and stress. The range of hybrid effect varies with hybrid ratio and the state of dispersion. The less hybrid ratio and the finer dispersion, the higher hybrid effect is. Sandwich construction with outlayer of carbon usually results in the least hybrid effect; meanwhile, the hybrid sequences with high degree of dispersion, such as intraply and alternate stacking, may produce relatively high hybrid effect, even though the hybrid ratio is large. So, degree of dispersion is the most significant factor governing the extent of hybrid effect.

The fracture modes of the hybrid composites are mainly governed by hybrid ratio, as well as degree of dispersion and interface bonding strength. Attributed to difference of hybrid ratio and degree of dispersion, there are four types of fracture modes for

carbon / glass hybrid fiber reinforced PES composites. In particular, the proper combination and sequences of the component materials may bring out the progressive multiple fracture mode of hybrid composites, so that the composites behave like ductile ones. In the case of multiple fracture, the toughness of matrix and interface strength between the fibers and matrix determine the length of two adjacent cracks and the length of delamination. In addition, the interface bonding affects the hybrid effect as well, which is proved by the appearance of a small amount of positive or negative hybrid effect in C / K hybrid composites with weak interface adhesion.

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TABLE 1 THE FUNDAMENTAL PROPERTIES
OF UNIDIRECTIONAL LAMINATES

Property (Test Standard)	CF / PES	GF / PES	KF / PES
0° Tension (ASTM D3039 -76)			
Modulus (GPa)	134 (1.3)	45.0 (1.9)	55.0 (0.5)
Strength (MPa)	1500 (8.3)	1200 (5.5)	1076 (4.2)
Elongation to failure (%)	1.12 (7.0)	2.66 (3.1)	1.73 (4.2)
Poisson's ratio	0.33 (4.0)	0.29 (4.0)	0.40 (7.5)
0° Flexure (ASTM D790M -84)			
Modulus (GPa)	110 (1.0)	40.0 (1.4)	43.7 (2.3)
Strength (MPa)	1577 (2.8)	1346 (3.8)	606 (0.9)
Short Beam Shear Strength (MPa) (ASTM D2344 -84)	86.5 (2.3)	72.3 (2.8)	42.3 (3.8)

Note: The figures in parentheses are coefficients of deviation.

TABLE 2 THE LAMINATE PARAMETERS OF HF / PES COMPOSITES

Symbol	Lay-up Sequence	V _f (%)	V _{LE} (%)	χ _{LE} (%)	χ _{cr} (%)
CG-1	(C ₂ CG ₂ CG ₂) _s	60.2	15.2	25.3	24.4
CG-2	(G ₂ CG ₅) _s	59.6	7.6	12.75	18.5
CG-3	(GC) _{4s}	59.9	29.8	49.7	22.5
CG-4	(C ₂ G ₆) _s	60.4	15.1	25.0	25.2
CG-5	(G ₅ C) _s	60.1	9.8	16.2	20.5
CG-7	H _{8s}	58.8	22.7	38.4	23.6
CG-8	(GH) _{4s}	57.7	11.1	19.3	19.0
CG-9	(GH') _{4s}	59.2	8.7	14.65	19.7
CK-1	(C ₂ K ₆) _s	59.9	14.7	24.9	22.7
CK-2	(C ₄ K ₄) _s	59.6	29.8	50.0	24.2
CK-3	(CK) _{4s}	59.9	30.4	50.8	27.4

Notes 1. V_f—Fiber volume fraction; V_{LE}—LE fiber volume fraction.

2. H and H' represent prepreps of intraply C / G hybrids with hybrid ratio of 38.4% and 28.9%.

TABLE 3 THE TENSILE PROPERTIES OF HYBRID PES COMPOSITES ^a

Sample	Initial Failure Stress σ_i (MPa)		Inferior Failure Stress σ_u (MPa)		Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Initial Failure Strain (%)	Hybrid Effect Re (%)
	Expt.	Est.	Expt.	Est.			
CG-1	927 (1.0) ^b	756		896	67.8 (0.4) ^b	1.36 (2.2) ^b	21.4
CG-2	904 (1.3)	631	(831)	1074	57.3 (1.2)	1.59 (2.5)	42.0
CG-3	1299 (0.6)	999		604	90.4 (1.7)	1.43 (1.5)	27.7
CG-4	907 (5.6)	753	931	900	67.2 (1.4)	1.33 (5.0)	18.8
CG-5	911 (1.2)	665	974	1006	60.0 (0.6)	1.51 (0.4)	34.8
CG-7	1104 (7.1)	886		739	79.8 (1.6)	1.39 (6.6)	24.1
CG-8	942 (4.6)	696	(505)	968	60.8 (0.7)	1.57 (1.6)	40.2
CG-9	891 (4.1)	650	(687)	1024	58.6 (0.0)	1.54 (2.0)	37.5
CK-1	817 (2.6)	836	704	808	75.5 (2.5)	1.14 (2.0)	1.5
CK-2	1079 (2.3)	1058	434	538	94.2 (1.9)	1.10 (1.4)	-1.8
CK-3	1016 (3.2)	1065		529	95.4 (1.6)	1.02 (1.6)	-8.9

^a The data are normalized to fiber volume fraction of 60%.

^b The figures between the parentheses are coefficients of deviation.

FIGURE 1 Tensile modulus against hybrid ratio

FIGURE 2 Hybrid effect against hybrid ratio.

FIGURE 3 Stress-strain curves showing four kinds of fracture modes: (a) one-step; (b) two-step; (c) intermediate mode; and (d) progressive multiple fracture.